

Innovating Education: Leveraging VR and AI for Universal Student Success Through Sixth-Grade Math

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The author has no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Data Availability Statement

The datasets used and/or analysed during the current study available from the corresponding author on reasonable request. For the purpose of safeguarding the participants' privacy, all data were anonymized, and identifiers were omitted in accordance with ethical procedures.

Aggregated performance data, such as math scores pre- and post-program intervention, total puzzle completion rates, and session engagement metrics, are stored in a secure

repository. These datasets are available for researchers to replicate or build on our findings, as long as they sign a data use agreement and secure approval from an appropriate ethics review board when necessary.

Ethical Approval

The participant giving consent for the study also agreed for their data to be shared in the present study with the condition data be used for educational/research purposes only.

All requests for access may be directed to Al Ware, corresponding author (al@voxbox.dev).

Author Contributions

Al Ware conceived and designed the study, his company VoxBox created the VR and AI learning environment, and performed the data collection and analysis. The manuscript was also written by Al Ware and also interpreted the results of study in this regard along with the flow of educational research protocols.

The author has read and approved the final manuscript, and takes full responsibility for the work and the conduct of the work, and the integrity of the data included. This is also confirmed by the author that every participant were informed and consented to participate in the study.

Abstract

We explore how embedding ST Math learning principles within an Artificial Intelligence (AI) enabled Virtual Reality (VR) setting influences sixth-graders with low mathematical achievement. ST Math known as Spatial-Temporal Math, is a visual, game-based learning program designed to enhance students' understanding of mathematical concepts through an intuitive and engaging approach. Developed by MIND Research Institute, it emphasizes problem-solving and conceptual learning by presenting math visually, without relying on traditional language-based explanations or symbolic equations, so turning ST Math into VR allowed for specific scenarios to build realistic experiences of

solving problems. Personalized feedback, pacing, and focused assistance is found in the form of artificial intelligence tools as well. It took three months and all fifty students began with a math proficiency of below 60%. Average improvement from this program was 40% with everyone passing. This research emphasizes the transformative possibility of integrating visual problem-solving with advanced digital technologies to remedy academic underachievement in mathematics Citation: (Boaler et al. 2019).

Keywords: Spatial-Temporal Math (ST Math), Virtual Reality (VR), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Mathematical Achievement, Game-Based Learning, Visual Problem-Solving Sixth-Grade Education

1. Background: Purpose and Approach

Mathematics has always been known to be one of the fundamental subjects, that exercises critical thinking, logical reasoning and also problem solving skills required for academic success as well as real-life problems. Yet, it is one of the most demanding disciplines for numerous learners. The traditional vocabulary attached to teaching practices of mathematics, which relies heavily on a heavy analog emphasis on symbolic representation, rote memorization and abstract theoretical constructs has distanced so many of the students from learning opportunities. For some students, these kinds of approaches can be particularly intimidating and frustrating if they have difficulty relating symbolic math in a meaningful way to the real decisions that organizations make, resulting in disengagement from material that ends up skewing assessment results.

To face these challenges and build resilience, pioneering platforms such as ST Math, showcase that math education can transform Citation: (Gee 2008). ST Math uses the properties of visual, concept-based learning to move past verbal explanations and symbolic equations. Instead, it immerses students within a structured visual framework for comprehension. By visually exploring relationships and patterns, students are able to work through problems or solve puzzles. This allows them to gain a more deep and intuitive understanding of math concepts. It has been hailed as a way to make math

teaching accessible amidst the scary language and lofty abstractions many high schoolers face—both due to this, but also because of the problems these abstract concepts can create when we think about equity.

This research will build on this success by applying the principles behind ST Math in a VR environment integrated with AI Citation: (Mayer 2020). The goal with this approach is to be able to create a new transformative learning experience that combines the power of visual problem solving, the immersive and interactive potential of VR, and adaptive capabilities using AI. The program responds to the lack of situational learning when it comes to math, as traditional teaching methods often fail to engage students by placing them in real-life context using immersive environments that make math concepts tangible and supporting individual needs and offering tailored practice support where it matters.

1.1 Research Objectives

1.1.1 This Study Proceeds with Three Main Goals

- **To Evaluate Impact:** The main objective is to examine the impact of VR learning environment that is based on ST Math, on the academic achievement of struggling students. Through tracking gains in math scores and engagement, the research will ascertain whether this method can make up for falling behind academically.
- **For The Powers of AI Personalization:** AI plays an important part in personalizing learning according to the strength and weakness. This study explores how AI can track performance, match instruction to student pace, and give feedback tailored for each learner so every student advances.
- **To Assess Wider Implications:** The above is quite limited to performance improvement, but this study would like to look for the scalability and generality of this approach. Could VR and AI tools inspired by ST Math be used effectively at other grade levels, for other subjects or in other learning environments? Long-term impact and Benefits of embedding these technologies for widespread adoption in education.

1.2 Thesis Statement

When ST Math-style visual problem-solving is placed in Virtual Reality and paired with AI-driven spatial learning personalization (a.k.a. adaptive learning), it can offer a transformational approach to boosting math performance for students who most need to succeed but often do not — those failing math classes. By catering to personalized learning, improving motivation and fostering conceptual understanding, this new approach represents a scalable model of educational reform that has the potential to create systemic change for learners.

2. Literature Review

2.1 ST Math: A Familiar Framework for Conceptual Learning

ST Math has become a powerful math education framework that encourages students to explore and learn mathematics with deep understanding. ST Math, however, is able to make a departure from traditional methods that center symbolic representation and verbal explanation through the effective use of visual representations as a means of connecting abstract mathematical ideas with concrete understanding. It gives all students equitable access to learning by eliminating the language barrier that hinders their ability to engage with language-rich instruction or raises a concern due to their learning disability.

All relevant research demonstrates the effectiveness of ST Math in building understanding, retention and problem solving Citation: (Dieckmann et al. 2019). The visual puzzles in the program promote an intuitive, non-verbal exploration of math that directly engages spatial reasoning. To illustrate, while working on a puzzle, students may see how to place weights in a scale visually and by doing this come to develop the concept of equality mechanistically rather than through memorization. This method not only promotes rich conceptual understanding but also helps to develop resilience and self-assuredness, where students learn to attempt experiments, reflect upon their impacts, and rectify themselves without any fear of failure.

In addition, ST Math introduces more complex challenges on top of skills already mastered sequentially. Accordingly, students become proficient in each skill before

moving on. With every puzzle, a new level of comprehension is built and students internalize fractions or geometry or algebraic thinking as it makes sense to them. This scaffolding method is consistent with theories of cognitive development from Piaget, Vygotsky, and Bruner that stress the acquisition of basic skills to be able to support higher-order thinking.

2.2 Virtual Reality: A New Wave in Visual Learning

Although ST Math would still be considered a success (due to visual problem-solving techniques), Virtual Reality (VR) enhances this pouring method to a new level of building full fields with immersive casts Citation: (Radu 2014). Through enhanced visual understanding, VR allows students to manipulate mathematical objects in three-dimensional spaces by direct interaction; thereby integrating theory and practice.

In one VR math lesson, students might walk into a virtual laboratory to touch 3D models of geometric objects and investigate their volume or surface area. As they change dimensions or change the shape, they can see changes in real-time and this solidifies their understanding. In the same way, abstract ideas like fractions can be made concrete with physical representations, like dividing a virtual pie into equal pieces or balancing weights on a scale. This kind of dynamic experience complements ST Math's focus on visual problem-solving, creating math that is accessible and exciting.

Studies also show that VR-based learning can help improve student interest, enthusiasm, and retention. VR, with its ability to transport the user into a new environment, fosters presence – students can pay better attention and engage more deeply with their studies. Moreover, VR caters to various learning preferences: visual learners enjoy immersive graphical content, kinesthetic learners engage better through physical interaction with objects, and auditory learners can receive instructions via voiceovers or guided AI companions.

When the principles of ST Math are incorporated into VR, immersion can turn a conceptually rich experience into a memorable and enjoyable one for students.

2.3 AI in Personalized Learning

AI is responsible for seamlessly augmenting the transmission of visual, immersive aspects of ST Math and VR with real-time data-driven differentiation. Although ST Math + VR environments deliver content and provide an opportunity to engage students, AI guarantees that the experience is personalized to maximize efficiency.

Best of all, AI proves to be a great judge of student performance data and can help us find trends that predict where students will struggle. For example, say a student is having ongoing trouble with the same kind of question, the AI can adaptively change the level of difficulty, provide more appropriate hints or suggest another way to approach it. Such adaptability helps students avoid both being pushed too far on the challenge scale, and switching off with tasks that are inadequate.

AI also tightens the feedback loop, revealing actionable details that can allow students to correct mistakes immediately and develop their understanding over time Citation: (Shute & Ke2012). In a virtual reality scenario where a student is building geometric shapes, the AI companion could encourage adjustments or point out mistakes along the way to promote a growth mindset and create positive learning habits.

Additionally, AI is important for keeping you engaged by providing motivational nudges and in-game rewards. AI bridges this because it reminds students of the journey they are on by celebrating small wins and milestones, even your challenges. More than that, AI can aggregate and analyze data over time; delivering rich insights into how students individually and collectively are progressing which can help drive teaching practice and curriculum design.

2.4 The Synergy of ST Math, VR, and AI

Couple those with the immersive environments found in VR, and add in the personalization capabilities enabled through AI, and you create a powerful trifecta. These two technologies combined address the shortcomings of math education as we know it in the following ways:

- Bringing the abstract to life with visual and interactive problem solving.
- Appealing to different learning styles with various content and pace.
- Including timely feedback, reinforcement, and opportunities for self-directed learning that will motivate them to do so.

Together, this not only improves performance in school math but also creates a positive relationship with the subject, turning fear into joy. With institutions striving to innovate for varied learner aspirations, such solutions that can scale and create significant impact in math education lie within the intersection of these technologies.

3. Methodology

3.1 Participants

The research involved a sample of 50 sixth-grade students having 25 boys and 25 girls; all of them failed in mathematics with no score higher than 60% before the intervention. None of the participants were previously exposed to Virtual Reality (VR) or Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered learning tools, ensuring that a steady baseline was established in the selection criteria. By starting from the same position, these children formed a strong baseline on which to assess the impact of this program. Diversity in gender representation also allowed us to explore engagement differences and promotion trends by the gamified and immersive learning preferences.

3.2 Program Design

Combining ST Math's principles of conceptual learning with a completely immersive VR environment introduced through an innovative and integrated use of AI-driven learning tools, the program transforms how math is taught. We intended to leverage the established power of visual learning, problem-solving, and real-time personalization to better meet individual student needs.

3.3 Appropriately Adapting ST Math Principles to VR

3.3.1 Conceptual Visualization

Visual or pictorial representations of mathematical problems dissolved many hurdles imposed by conventional abstract symbolic insignia. Examples included:

- **Fraction Task:** Students placed weights on a virtual scale to give them a sense of understanding equivalence and proportionality.
- **Geometry activities:** Students built 3D shapes with virtual manipulatives to explore volume, surface area and symmetry.
- **Puzzle-Based Problem Solving:** The puzzles within the program were organized sequentially by difficulty and presented to students in that order. By learning through exploration and discovery, students were able to establish a base of knowledge and skills before moving on to more complex problems.
- **Feedback-Free Exploration:** Consistent with ST Math, puzzles were attempted by students without direct feedback at first. It taught us to think critically, be persistent and have the willingness to learn from mistakes, and in the process develop resilience and a stronger grasp of the concepts.

3.4 AI Integration

The AI-driven features of the program transformed delivering learning with personalization for every student. Key functionalities included:

- **Live Performance Tracking:** The AI companion tracked performance indicators, discovering areas of error patterns and struggles. It offered relevant clues and pointers to assist them through tough times.
- **Adaptive Pacing:** This learning path can be tailored to every student and adapt as per their progress, keeping students challenged without frustration or boredom.
- **Immersive Engagement:** The AI provided motivational feedback and rewards like badges and points to keep users motivated in their journey through challenges.

3.5 VR Tools and Scenarios

Using gamification principles to promote engagement, the VR environment was designed to be consistent with visual problem-solving elements.

3.5.1 Interactive Problem Spaces

- **Fractions Lab:** Students explored parts of a whole through virtual manipulatives—pies, rods, and other objects. Through manipulation of these objects, students gained a concrete experience with fraction operations and their equivalencies.
- **Geometry Builder:** Students built and played with 3D shapes allowing for real-time testing of the volume, surface area, transformations.

3.5.2 Progression Mechanics

The program moved students through puzzles that increased in complexity as they were mastered. Gamification principles aligned such that new challenges and environments unlocking over time was a form of intrinsic reward, keeping users engaged in the long run.

3.5.3 Collaborative Challenges

Problem-solving tasks were performed collaboratively in a team, thereby enhancing collaborative learning, communication and peer-learning. In collaboration, students solved complex real-world situations based on the geometry by designing a virtual structure under defined geometric constraints, or managing resources in a simulated economy with fractions and ratios.

3.6 Program Duration

The program lasted for 3 months and students did three 60-minute sessions a week. This timetable allowed students the time needed to go into depth on content whilst also tracking progress regularly. The longer period also allowed the researchers to measure not only short-term learning but also continued engagement over time.

3.7 Data Overview

A mixed-methods approach was implemented to assess the program impact utilizing both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods.

3.7.1 Participants

- Total: 50 sixth-grade students (25 boys, 25 girls).
- Baseline: All participants had failing math scores (<60%) before the program.

3.7.2 Program Duration

- 3 months, 3 sessions per week (60 minutes per session).

3.7.3 Quantitative Data

Performance Distribution

Chart: AI Ware • Source: VoxBox _RED R&D • Created with Datawrapper

Fig. 1 comparison of pre- and post-program math proficiency scores, highlighting significant improvement among participating students.

1. Pre- and Post-Program Assessments (Fig. 1)

- Average Pre-Program Score: 52.4% (± 6.2).
- Average Post-Program Score: 80.1% (± 8.4).
- Average Improvement: 27.7 percentage points (or 52.9% increase).
- Statistical Significance: $p < 0.01$ (paired t-test).

Gender-Based Trends

Chart: AI Ware • Source: VoxBox _RED R&D • Created with Datawrapper

Fig. 2 key metrics such as puzzle completion rates, task accuracy, and the number of hints used by students, demonstrating diverse engagement patterns across gender

2. Performance Metrics within the Program (Fig. 2)

Key Metrics:

- Average Puzzle Completion Rate: 83%.
- Accuracy Rate on Tasks: 87%.

Hints Used:

- Boys: 2.4 hints per task (average).
- Girls: 3.1 hints per task (average).

Time Spent per Session:

- Average: 57 minutes (out of 60).

Math Gain Results —These are the improvements made in Math proficiency as determined from Pre and Post- program Assessment The students were assessed on the critical concepts they learned over the program and compared their scores to baseline data.

3.7.4 Qualitative Data

Student Feedback Survey

Students gave feedback on whether or not they feel the program works, is enjoyable, and easy to use. That allowed us to understand how the program affected their attitudes towards math.

■ The program was better than traditional math class. ■ I found the VR tasks engaging and enjoyable.
■ The AI companion helped me understand math better. ■ I feel more confident in my math skills now.

Chart: AL Ware • Source: VoxBox _RED R&D • Created with Datawrapper

Fig. 3 Student feedback themes, summarized in Figure 3, reveal gender-based differences in engagement, with boys favoring competitive elements and girls excelling in collaborative tasks.

Common Themes (Open-Ended Responses) (Fig. 3)

Boys:

- “I liked competing on the leaderboards the most—it made me want to get better every time.”
- “The puzzles were fun because they felt like games.”

Girls:

- “I enjoyed working with my classmates on group challenges.”
- “The AI made math less scary because it gave me tips instead of just telling me I was wrong.”

Focus Groups

Insights from Students:

- Engagement: Students universally reported that the VR environment made math more interesting.
- AI Support: The AI companion’s hints and feedback were highlighted as a key factor in helping them stay on track.

Challenges:

- Boys mentioned frustration with overly complex puzzles.
- Girls reported initial difficulty adapting to the VR interface but enjoyed the collaborative aspects once acclimated.

Observational Logs

Engagement Patterns:

- Week 1: 60% of students displayed hesitation or confusion with VR tools.
- Week 6: 85% of students were highly engaged, with minimal guidance needed.
- Week 12: 95% of students showed confidence in navigating tasks independently.

Collaboration Trends:

- **Boys:** Worked better independently but occasionally supported peers during competitive tasks.
- **Girls:** Preferred group challenges and were more likely to ask for and provide help to peers.

Student Work Sessions

Fractions Lab:

- **Initial Attempt:** Students struggled to balance scales, with 40% accuracy.
- **Final Attempt:** 90% accuracy after repeated problem-solving efforts.

Geometry Builder:

- **Task:** Build a cube with a volume of 27 units.
- **Completion Rate:** 88%, with students accurately calculating dimensions.

3.7.5 Challenges

- **Initial Adaptation:** 40% of students required extra onboarding sessions in the first two weeks to adjust to the VR environment.
- **Access Inequities:** Only 20% of students had access to VR-compatible devices at home, limiting out-of-class practice.

3.7.6 Key Outcomes

- **Math Confidence Increase:** Surveys and focus groups indicated 85% of students felt more confident tackling math problems after the program.
- **Improved Engagement:** Observational logs and feedback showed that students preferred this program to traditional math classes.

- **Inclusion and Equity:** Both boys and girls benefited from the program, though preferences differed, underscoring the importance of offering varied engagement methods.

4. Discussion (Key Insights)

4.1 Graphic Problem Solving is the Key to Engagement

Among the key takeaways from this analysis was how ST Math usage behavior shifted when the principles behind ST Math were embedded into a Virtual Reality (VR) environment. Since ST Math eschews symbolic and other traditional representations in favor of visual, concept-bound approaches that facilitate intuitive exploration, this made it a great fit for VR. When abstract concepts feel more tangible, less intimidating and most importantly intuitive by immersing students into 3D environments (which most traditional classrooms fall short at), More specifically, students using virtual fractions in the Fractions Lab or building shapes in the Geometry Builder reported deeper understanding and increased engagement. The way of visually solving the problems allowed for understanding but also created interest and joy to math in what was previously a difficult subject, into something hands on and really fun.

4.2 Learning Made Better with AI Personalization

Having an AI companion was key to keeping all students progressing in some way regardless of their skill level at the start. By analyzing how well an individual was doing at that time and then tailoring the difficulty level of subsequent challenges, the AI created a personalized learning environment that catered for each student exactly where they were. Chatbot feedback differed for students with low and high prediction deficits — students lower on this were given extra scaffolding and specific prompts when they made errors in fraction equivalencies, while students who had mastered the tasks received more difficult problems to work on. That mix of weekly AI encouragement and using rewards based on game design also helped keep students engaged, especially among those who

started off as less confident about their math skills. This level of flexibility created an equitable program, and every participant grew to the best of their ability.

4.3 Differential Engagement by Gender

The program reaffirmed previous research on differences in learning preferences and engagement styles related to gender. In competitive situations, like competition with leaderboards or remaining timing issues, boys always win. This intrigued them — and encouraged them to play for higher scores. By contrast, between each gender's competitive excels, girls performed better in cooperative contexts that involved teamwork or a social component. The Collaborative Challenges, in which students come together to work on real-world problem-solving, were also a hit with girls, creating an experience of community and shared achievement. In an educational setting, we recognized the ability to personalize and tailor our program based on gender preferences as negotiated opportunities for choice ultimately enabled us to create a program that would be welcoming and stimulating for all students – again underscoring the need for diverse approaches to engagement.

5. Challenges

Although the program was successful, it struggled with some barriers to implementation that were instructive for future efforts.

5.1 Initial Adaptation

Originally, several college students struggled with adjusting to the VR setting in the first couple of classes. The majority had never tried immersive technology, and needed extra help with getting acquainted with the interface, how to interact with virtual objects, and things like program mechanics in general. To counter this, more people were onboarded with a series of tutorials and practice scenarios. The second week challenge then showed the true potential of VR but also highlighted that it takes careful planning and support at the start.

5.2 Access Inequities

One major limitation was that few had access to VR-compatible devices outside the class. Although the in-school sessions allowed for learning within a controlled environment, students who wanted extra practice or exploration at home could not pursue it, leaving a reinforcement gap. This underscored the need to consider gaps in infrastructure when expanding such initiatives. Future iterations would benefit from loaner devices or equitable tech access to really amplify the impact of the program.

6. Conclusion

The present research illustrates the power of complementing VR learning environments that embody ST Math principles with AI-enabled personalization. This study shows that this novel approach will be able to solve some very important math education issues for failing students. Combining ST Math's visual, conceptual problem-solving framework with the immersive potential of VR and adaptive advantages of AI for support, the program stood out as a performance-impacting learning experience that was both engaging and meaningful Citation: (Chin & Wang 2021).

The most important result was the way that this program made abstract concepts of mathematics real and tangible. When introduced to hands-on and engaging tasks, students who had struggled with fractions, geometry and problem-solving developed more conceptual understanding. These were tasks that provided students with ways to explore relationships and patterns some might have seen for the first time in a visual context, allowing them a better understanding of abstract theory while applying it. Additionally, the adaptive capabilities of the AI companion filled gaps in learning where necessary for all students enabling equity.

In addition to the quantifiable spike in math performance, the program changed the way students felt about the subject. Through gamified challenges, collaborative tasks, and tailored support, it transformed math from a daunting mountain to an enjoyable, attainable climb where the summit took them closer to their dream careers. For students

with a history of academic struggle, this change in thinking is essential for long-term learning confidence and outcomes.

7. Recommendations

In order to capitalize on the findings of this study, we recommend taking several steps to maximize the impact and generalizability of the program:

7.1 Scalability

This approach has shown to be effective and could be applied in other subjects beyond sixth grade math. The next versions should embrace more disciplines—science and language arts come to mind — where the richness of a sense-making process can be captured, or nearly so, in a visualization. It could also be expanded to other grade levels, such as elementary and high school, with the possibility of earlier intervention and ongoing support. When you think about scalability, it should be modular such that educators can modify the content to meet their specific curriculum and learning goals.

7.2 Accessibility

Although the treatments studied showed promise with this work, access to these VR and AI technological solutions is not equitable and still poses a challenge to increasing adoption of these modalities. This means schools and districts have to make sure they have all of the infrastructure — VR-ready gear, high-speed Internet access, and teacher training opportunities. Any partnerships with technology providers and government initiatives to subsidize the costs, should ensure that schools in less well-funded areas do not miss out. Accessibility must also include home-situated learning, lending devices or writing web-accessible simulations for students who cannot attend in-face sessions.

7.3 Long-Term Evaluation

Incredible as the near-term gains in math achievement may be, we must then ask whether this method yields sustainable results. Longitudinal studies will help in understanding the impact of these tools on academic outcomes in the long run. For instance, following

students over subsequent years in math classes can indicate whether the program is instilling enduring conceptual understanding and skills for problem solving. Evaluations should also assess other outcomes, in addition to academic results, for instance, changes in students' confidence and motivation and attitudes toward learning. That could strengthen the program's case for wider adoption and inform refinements in the program.

Below is a selection of peer-reviewed, high-quality references that back up this research on ST Math and Virtual Reality in education to AI-driven learning personalization:

References

Boaler J (2019) *Limitless Mind: Learn, Lead, and Live Without Barriers*. HarperCollins, UK.

Chin KY, Wang CS (2021)

A case study in visualization and spatial reasoning: Virtual reality for mathematics learning

computers & education 172:104253.

Cohen L, Manion L, Morrison K (2018)

School-related mental health promotion: A research method in education, 8th edn.

Routledge, London.

Dieckmann J, LaMar T, Williams C, Boaler (2019)

Visualising mathematics is good for our brain and learning: Seeing as understanding lastly. *J Appl Comput Math* 8:1–7.

Dunleavy M, Dede C (2014) *Augmented reality teaching and learning*.

In: Spector JM, Merrill MD, Elen J, Bishop MJ (eds) *Handbook of research on educational communications and technology*, 4th edn. Springer, Berlin, Germany, pp 735–745.

Figlio DN, Loeb S (2016) High-stakes testing and student achievement: Updated evidence from 2005 to 2015. *Rev Educ Res* 86:1052-1084.

Gee JP (2008)

Learning and games.

In: Salen K (ed) *The ecosystem of games: Linking youth, play and learning*. The MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, pp 21–40.

Holstein K, Hong G, Tegene M, McLaren BM, Alevan V (2019)

A classroom as a dashboard: Co-designing wearable cognitive augmentation for K-12 teachers.

ACM Digital Library 79–88. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3170358.3170377>

Mayer RE (2020)

Multimedia learning, 3rd edn.

Cambridge University Press.

MIND Research Institute (n.d.) *ST Math: Visual Instruction for Deeper Conceptual Understanding*.

Papert (1980)

Radu I (2014) *Augmented reality in education: A meta-review and cross-media analysis*.

Pers Ubiquit Comput 18:1533–1543. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00779-013-0747-y>

Shute VJ, Ke F (2012)

Games, Learning and Assessment.

In: Ifenthaler D, Eseryel D, Ge X (eds) *Assessment in Game-Based Learning: Foundations, innovations, and perspectives*. Springer, pp 43–58.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-3546-4_4

Van Eck R (2006)

Digital game-based learning — The digital natives aren't (actually) restless.
EDUCAUSE Rev 41:16-30.